

Overall study design

Title of the study	Mouse kidney tubule dissections		
Document creation date	03/27/2024	Corresponding Email	julio.lopes-sampaio@curie.fr
Principle investigator	Prof. Nicolas Pallet	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Universite Paris Cite	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	2-step extraction
pH adjustment	8	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

Which solvent was used	IPA:Methanol:Chloroform(4:2:1) + Amonium acetate	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	Orbitrap	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	17500
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
Direct type	Chip	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	No
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank		

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	No
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	No
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Raw data upload	No
Are metadata available?	No	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

dissected mouse kidney tubules / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	-	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	sn Position	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
-FA2(-H)-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

1) DG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
DG 17:0 17:0	DG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	One factor for all species	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) PC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

2) PC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 17:0 17:0	PC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

3) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name FA2(+O) -FA2(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

3) PC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard Endogenous subclass PC 17:0 17:0 PCO			
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

4) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name FA1(+O) FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

4) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 17:0 17:0	PE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
-FA2(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

5) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE 17:0 17:0	PEO		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

6) PG[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

6) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PG 17:0 17:0	PG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

7) PA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PA	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

7) PA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PA 17:0 17:0	PA		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

8) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
-FA2(-H)			
HG(PI,241)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

8) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PI 16:0 16:0	PI		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

9) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Identification level	sn Position	Check isomer overlap	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Limit of detection	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
GP(153)			
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Background check at MS1	Yes		

9) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PS 17:0 17:0	PS		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

10) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

10) LPC[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 12:0	LPC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

11) LPC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

11) LPC O[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC 12:0	LPCO		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

12) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

12) LPE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE 17:1	LPE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

13) LPE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE O	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

13) LPE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE 17:1	LPE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

14) LPA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPA	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

14) LPA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPA 17:0	LPA		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

15) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

15) LPS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

16) Cer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

16) Cer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Cer 18:1;2 12:0	Cer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

17) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+CH3COO]-	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

17) HexCer[M+CH3COO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
GalCer 18:1;2 12:0	HexCer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

18) Hex2Cer[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H]+	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

18) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LacCer 18:1;2 12:0	HexCer2		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

19) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex3Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

19) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Gb3 18:1;2 16:0(D9)	Hex3Cer		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

20) GB4[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GB4	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

20) GB4[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Gb3 18:1;2 16:0(D9)	Gb4		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

21) GM3[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GM3	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

21) GM3[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
GM3 18:1;2 18:0(D5)	GM3		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

22) SM[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

22) SM[M+H]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM 18:1;2 12:0	SM		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

23) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

23) ST[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Chol(D6)	Cholesterol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

24) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

24) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
CE 16:0(D7)	CE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

25) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check isomer overlap	No
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	LipidXplorer
Isotope correction at MS1	Type 2	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

25) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	LipidXplorer
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TG 17:0 17:0 17:0	TG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		